

SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TVL PROFICIENCY AND GRADUATES EMPLOYMENT READINESS: BASES FOR ENHANCED CURRICULUM PROGRAM

ROCHELLE M. SORIANO

grhian20@gmail.com

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City

ABSTRACT

This study made use of the descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship of MSEMSAT Senior High School TVL Department Students' proficiency and their readiness for employment. This study focused on identifying if the SHS-TVL students' proficiency is related to their preparedness to be employed. From the data gathered, it was found out that the perception of the respondents in the SHS-TVL proficiency related variables is not significantly related to the employment readiness of graduates which was partially supported in this study. Meaning, even if the graduates' proficiency is high, they do not automatically perceive that they are ready for employment. Also, the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between the perception of the respondents in SHS-TVL proficiency related variables when they are group according to their TVL major course" presented in the study was not sustained in this undertaking. From this, it can be deduced that even though the students do learn the skills and therefore have a high proficiency in their respective specialties, this does not necessarily mean that they are employment ready. Hence, this singular factor is not enough to say that they are ready to be a part of the working force. This could also mean that to be employment-ready, one must have more than high proficiency in their respective specialties. Based on these findings, the researcher recommends a much stronger support to the SHS-TVL program from the DepEd policy makers through the formulation of guidelines and policies regarding the enhancement of the curriculum to further strengthen the program. This could be done by aligning the expectations of the learners to the objectives of the programs.

Keywords: SHS-TVL Proficiency, Employment Readiness, Skills Requisite, Cookery, EIM (Electrical Installation and Maintenance), SMAW (Shielded Metal Arc Welding).